

Simulation Analysis of a PLPDA mounted on a UAV using Hybrid Solver Methods

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Abstract— Evaluating the performance of an antenna in the presence of electrically large structures is computationally challenging. In this context, three solver techniques – full-wave Finite Integration Technique (FIT), Unidirectional Advanced Method (UAM) and Hybrid Bidirectional Solver (HBS) are compared. The above solver techniques available in Computer Simulation Technology Microwave Studio (CST-MWS) are used to simulate a Printed Log-Periodic Dipole Antenna (PLPDA) enclosed in a fixture with foam mounted on an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV). The electromagnetic performance of all three solver methods is compared, thereby validating the accuracy, with realized gain differences of less than 0.2 dB, HPBW differences of less than 1°, and front-to-back ratio differences of less than 2-3 dB at all frequencies. The full-wave FIT solver takes 14 hrs at 6 GHz, but the UAM and HBS only take 1.2 and 1.6 hrs, respectively. In contrast to the HBS, the UAM offers the most computationally efficient solution for this class of problems by incorporating selective field recalculations that take into consideration the presence of the UAV body.

Index Terms— Full-wave Finite Integration Technique (FIT), hybrid solver, Multilevel Fast Multipole Method (MLFMM), Printed Log-Periodic Dipole Antenna (PLPDA), Unidirectional Advanced Method (UAM), Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV).

I. INTRODUCTION

With the development in wireless communication technologies, fifth generation (5G) and beyond

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plays a pivotal role in establishing reliable connectivity. Establishing communication links between users and establishing wireless connectivity between different use cases, such as automobiles, smart devices, and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), are essential for the Internet of Things (IoT). Before fabricating a prototype or assembling communication equipment with an antenna, antenna performance should be rigorously validated. Validating an antenna as a standalone component or evaluating its performance when assembled with communication equipment can be performed by solving Maxwell’s equations. To solve Maxwell’s equations and estimate the performance of antennas, there has been a great improvement in Computational Electromagnetics (CEM). Electromagnetic (EM) simulations can be performed with algorithms such as Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) and Finite Element Method (FEM), which solve Maxwell’s equations in differential form; or the Method of Moments (MoM), and Finite Integration Technique (FIT), which solve these equations in integral form. To efficiently solve these equations with precision while reducing the computational burden, the authors in [1] proposed sub-gridding techniques based on FDTD. By using the concept of sub-gridding, users can maintain dense meshing at the required geometric areas of the antennas and coarse meshing at other parts of the antenna [2]. FDTD operates in the time domain and is well-suited for broadband analysis. For narrowband applications, FEM, which solves the EM problem in integral form in the frequency domain, is a popular choice. FEM often simulates the structure in a queuing strategy, i.e. one frequency at a time, rather than solving the EM problem in one go, capturing the EM behavior over a wide range of frequencies as FDTD does. Due to this FEM achieves higher accuracy than FDTD, but at the cost of an increased computational effort, resulting in a higher simulation time and higher Random Access Memory (RAM) requirements. To overcome computational load, authors in [3] developed a goal-oriented algorithm for the FEM. In the developed algorithm, the computational load was reduced by limiting the extent to which adaptive meshing is performed at each frequency point.

Similar to FEM and FDTD, FIT is widely used to simulate EM problems. FIT converts partial differential equations into a discrete set of algebraic equations by integrating over control volumes with hexahedral cells in the computational domain.

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FIT is commonly used for geometries with sharp edges [4]. To reduce the computational load while retaining the simulation accuracy, a space-time FIT is useful. In space-time FIT, gridding is extended into both space and time for local refinement to capture the EM behavior at a higher resolution in critical regions. On the other hand, for applications with medium complexity and for geometries involving surface meshing, such as conducting objects and electrically thin structures, MoM is a popular choice. MoM, which succeeds in simulating small to medium-sized EM problems, has high computational requirements for simulating electrically large structures. To overcome these computational challenges, MoM uses the Multilevel Fast Multipole Method (MLFMM). The MLFMM succeeds in reducing RAM usage by dividing the computational domain into several levels based on a multilevel structure.

To simulate antenna arrays or antennas in the presence of electrically large structures using full-wave solvers based on FIT, MoM, FDTD, or FEM requires relatively large computational resources. To address these challenges in terms of computational load and simulation time, several techniques such as Domain Decomposition Methods (DDM), parallel programming schemes, and the use of hybrid solver techniques have been developed. To analyze the radiation patterns of antennas placed close to electrically large platforms, researchers have adopted several techniques. Simulating both the antenna and the platform in a single full-wave solver is the most accurate method. However, when the platform is electrically large, simulating the complete structure in a single solver demands high computational resources and can sometimes be impractical. To address these challenges, hybrid solver techniques have been developed as presented in Table I. For instance, a combination of the Fast Dipole Method (FDM) and Physical Optics (PO) has been used to simulate antennas on large platforms, such as submarines [5]. This method accelerates matrix-vector multiplications (MVMs) for both MoM and PO regions using the FDM technique. The computational efficiency is enhanced by using a Taylor series expansion for distant interactions and the Equivalent Dipole Moment method for near-field pairs. However, the method's assumptions and approximations, such as the Taylor series expansion for distant calculations, may introduce errors in complex or highly detailed structures, making it suitable only for specific scenarios.

Another hybrid method combines the Multilevel Fast Multipole Algorithm (MLFMA) and PO to efficiently analyze antennas on electrically large platforms [6]. This method leverages the efficient iterative MoM-PO strategy and the Bitmap Index (BI) method to reduce computational costs and storage consumption while maintaining accuracy. The efficient iterative MoM-PO strategy avoids the direct calculation of the coupling matrix (Z_{PO}) by evaluating its contribution to the excitation voltage vector, reducing computational usage. The BI method stores shadowing effect coefficients, significantly reducing storage space compared to conventional methods. However, the interaction between the antenna region and the

platform region is loosely coupled, and the BI method's approximations can lead to inaccuracies when there is strong coupling (tightly coupled) between the antenna and the platform. Tightly coupled refers to cases when an antenna is in proximity with an external structure effecting the performance of an antenna. In our case the Printed Log-Periodic Dipole Antenna (PLPDA) and the UAV are separated by less than $\lambda/4$ distance resulting in tightly coupled scenario [7]. Other hybrid methods which aim in reducing the computational utilization are achieved by combining fitting Green's function fast Fourier transform with PO to calculate radiation from antennas mounted on electrically large conducting platforms [8]. To improve the accuracy of simulation results for hybrid solver techniques, it is important to consider the tight coupling between the antenna and the platform. Addressing the coupling issues authors in [9] propose a combination of MLFMA and Modified Adaptive Division Beam Tracing (MADBT) algorithm. Moreover, MADBT analyzes the antennas mounted on large, complex platforms. The MLFMA is used for the antenna and the transition region, while the MADBT method is employed to analyze the platform, considering multi-bounce effects. The MADBT method replaces the conventional PO method for analyzing the platform, allowing for the consideration of multi-bounce effects. The key advantage of MADBT is that interaction between the MLFMA antenna and MADBT platform regions is handled iteratively. This allows MADBT to handle the coupling between antenna and platform with higher accuracy. However, this method has some drawbacks as well, particularly the use of approximations, such as the point source modeling and adaptive beam tracing used by MADBT, which may introduce errors when analyzing the effect of electric fields from antenna to the platform.

In [10], the Equivalence Principle Algorithm (EPA) combined with high-frequency asymptotic models are used for simulating antennas near electrically large structures. The hybrid method combines the MoM with high-frequency asymptotic models, such as PO [11], where the antenna is solved in the MoM region considering the effects of the nearby electrically large platform. The platform is solved in the PO region where the Schur complement is utilized to simplify the interaction between different domains. The Schur complement approach reduces computational effort by focusing on the most significant interactions. The proposed method is validated by simulating a dipole near a curved plate. Results obtained from the proposed hybrid method are compared with full-wave solvers which shows good agreement. Though the proposed hybrid method reduces computational effort by focusing on the most significant interactions, there are some drawbacks to this method. A major limitation of this method stems from the iterations performed by the Schur complement method. The Schur complement approach requires normalization with the inverse Gramian after translation to the PO functions and back. Compared to the Direct PO method, the Schur complement approach is computationally expensive due to its multiple iterations and normalization requirements. In each iteration, the EM radiation from the non-Schur-complement domains must

TABLE I
HYBRID SOLVER TECHNIQUES

Reference	Antenna region	Platform region	Limitations
[5]	FDM	PO	Inaccuracies from Taylor series expansion
[6]	MLFMA	PO	Method fails during strong coupling between antenna and platform
[8]	Fitting Greens function fast Fourier transform	PO	Edge diffraction and weak currents are neglected
[9]	MLFMA	MADBT	Adaptive beam tracing could result inaccuracies
[10, 11]	MoM	PO	Fails for complex geometries
[12]	FIT	Iterative PO	Iterative PO is based on approximations
[13]	MoM	Transition matrix (Spherical Vector Waves)	Is applicable only when the shape of the structure in platform region is Canonical (Sphere)
[14]	Dipole moment	FEM	Proposes using FEM for the platform, but it is CPU-intensive and becomes inefficient for electrically large structures
[15]	MoM	UTD	Considers only far-field regions
[16]	Higher order MoM	Calderon projection operator with Fast Multipole Method (FMM)	Fails when the platform has irregular geometry
This work	FIT accelerated by GPU	MoM with MLFMM	Works for antennas operating over wide frequency bands, reduces computational resources in terms of RAM, GPU usage and simulation time, while maintaining the accuracy.

be computed along with the scattering from the domains handled by PO methods. Because calculations are performed in two different domains, these simulations face challenges in satisfying the convergence criteria. While Table I presents different hybrid solver approaches for simulating an antenna mounted on an electrically large platform, several simulation attempts have been made to validate the performance of an antenna mounted on a UAV. UAV-based applications utilize many Radio Frequency (RF) instruments either for establishing communication links with the ground or for obtaining latitude, longitude, and altitude information. These RF instruments include Global Positioning System (GPS), telemetry equipment, antennas, portable spectrum analyzers, and signal generators. These systems operate in various frequency bands, including 1 to 4 GHz (L-band), 4 to 8 GHz (C-band), and 8 to 12 GHz (X-band). RF instruments such as portable signal generators and spectrum analyzers are essential for UAV-based antenna measurements. Typically, these devices are not mounted on a single UAV. To address the challenges such as ground reflections in UAV-based antenna measurements, two UAVs can be independently configured: one as a transmitter equipped with a portable signal generator, and the other as a receiver with a portable spectrum analyzer. This non-tethered setup enables the UAVs to maintain high altitudes, thereby minimizing the impact of ground reflections [17, 18]. When a UAV is equipped with RF equipment, it is essential to ensure that the RF equipment mounted on the UAV is free from EM coupling between them and the UAV body itself. To evaluate the performance of RF equipment mounted on a UAV, researchers in [19] performed full-wave simulations. All simulations were performed using the Computer Simulation Technology Microwave Studio (CST-MWS). Based on the simulation results, the positions of the antennas and RF equipment utilized for either receiving/transmitting purposes were optimized to avoid EM coupling [20].

Combining MLFMM and PO, researchers in [21] evaluated the performance of a omnidirectional antenna and a directional antenna when mounted on a UAV. Simulations were performed using FEKO with antennas simulated using MLFMM, and the UAV simulated using PO. Similarly, in Ansys High Frequency Structure Simulator (HFSS), commonly used hybrid solver configurations are FEM for antenna and Integral Equation (IE) or Shooting Bouncing Rays for the platform [22]. It should be noted that the performance of an antenna mounted on a UAV depends on the antenna type and the frequency of operation of the antenna. Considering these aspects, the performance of the omnidirectional antenna operating in the 2 to 4 GHz (S-band) and a directional antenna operating in the C-band when mounted on the UAV wings and UAV fuselage locations were evaluated. The use of PO reduces the simulation time and computational load; however, PO provides accurate results when the UAV is electrically large, such as an electrical size of 300λ in the C-band.

Similarly, to evaluate the performance of a conformal array and an array of microstrip patch antennas, researchers in [23] performed simulations involving a vertically polarized conformal microstrip patch antenna and an array of microstrip patch antennas mounted on a UAV. Both the micro-strip antenna and its array are simulated in the X-Band. To reduce the computational load for simulating an antenna mounted on a UAV, [24] proposed the use of the Electric Field Integral Equation (EFIE) and Electric/Magnetic Current Combined Field Integral Equation (JMCFIE) accelerated by MLFMA. The proposed algorithm EFIE-JMCFIE is a frequency domain method that requires only a portion of the platform to evaluate the performance of the antenna mounted on the UAV. This reduces the computational complexity of the simulations by reducing computational resources and simulation time. The same antennas when mounted on the UAV are simulated in CST MWS. The radiation patterns of the microstrip antenna

Fig. 1. Simulation setup for hybrid solvers such as UAM and HBS.

mounted on the UAV, simulated using EFIE-JMCFIE and CST, were compared with the measured values. From these comparisons, it is observed that in the main lobe area, the results from EFIEJMCFIE and CST are in good agreement with the measured values. However, in the side-lobe regions, results from the CST MWS are more accurate when compared with the measured values. This is because the EFIE-JMCFIE considers only a portion of the UAV body for simulations, therefore CST MWS provides better accuracy.

In this article, we propose the use of hybrid solver techniques to simulate a PLPDA mounted on a UAV. We propose the use of Unidirectional Advanced Method (UAM) based on commercially available EM tools such as CST-MWS. In the UAM, a PLPDA is simulated using transient FIT solver which is accelerated by an Nvidia RTX4090 Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) and the UAV is simulated using MoM. For simulating the PLPDA using the full-wave FIT solver, a discrete edge port with a 50-ohm impedance match was used to excite the antenna. The computational efficiency of UAM is investigated by benchmarking and comparing the simulation time, RAM, and GPU usage with the HBS, and the full-wave FIT solver. Moreover, the accuracy of the UAM is evaluated by comparing the radiation patterns of the PLPDA obtained with the HBS and with the full-wave FIT solvers. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we explain the formulation of the Hybrid Solver Technique. In Section III, UAM is validated for a PLPDA mounted on an electrically large structure, such as a UAV. Here, we explain the principle behind UAM and the reasons why UAM is computationally more efficient than the iterative HBS.

II. FORMULATION OF HYBRID SOLVER TECHNIQUES

When compared with full-wave FIT solvers, hybrid solvers such as UAM and HBS reduce the simulation time and computational resources by simulating the antenna and the electrically large structure in separate solvers. To utilize the maximum efficiency of each solver, the usual combination is FIT/FEM for the antenna and MoM/PO for the electrically large structure. This helps maintain independent meshing in the

selected solver rather than having very dense meshing for both the antenna and the electrically large structure in a single solver [25-27]. In terms of meshing, FIT discretizes Maxwell's equations on a staggered hexahedral mesh, FEM employs tetrahedral elements suitable for electrically small structures, while MoM and PO utilize surface-based triangular patches, making them appropriate for electrically large structures.

While performing simulations with either UAM or HBS, PLPDA simulated in FIT is often referred to as the source and components in proximity to the source, i.e. the UAV is referred to as the platform. The simulation setup for a hybrid solver technique along with the UAV configured as transmitter (PLPDA mounted on a hexacopter) is shown in Fig. 1. As shown in Fig. 1, UAM creates two regions: the source domain and field exchange region. The source domain consists of the surface currents created over the PLPDA surface represented by a Field Source Monitor (FSM), and the field exchange region is used to calculate the coupling from the source to the platform and platform to the source. Both HBS and UAM operate based on the Surface Equivalence Theorem (SET). SET allows a complex EM problem to be simplified by replacing the electric (J) and magnetic (M) currents with equivalent electric surface (J_s) and magnetic surface (M_s) currents on a closed surface S . As per the SET, J_s and M_s produce the same EM fields outside or inside the surface S as the original source. These equivalent surface currents are given by,

$$J_s = \hat{n} \times H, \quad (1)$$

$$M_s = -\hat{n} \times E, \quad (2)$$

where H is the magnetic field on the surface, E is the electric field on the surface, and \hat{n} is the outward normal unitary vector to the surface S . Based on the SET after simulating the PLPDA by FIT, the equivalent surface currents defined in the field exchange region are exported as a field source monitor. A field source monitor consists of the tangential E and H fields on a surface at the specified frequencies. In our case, we have separate field source monitors at 0.8, 3.5, 4.3 and 6 GHz. The

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Fig. 2. Simulated and measured radiation patterns of PLPDA enclosed in a fixture with foam mounted on a UAV in azimuth cut at (a) 0.8, (b) 3.5, (c) 4.3, and (d) 6 GHz.

calculated J_s and M_s are used to estimate the EM coupling between the source and the platform [24]. During simulations, both UAM and HBS techniques consider the EM coupling from the platform when simulating the source in the FIT and the EM coupling from the source when simulating the platform in the MoM. When calculating the coupling from platform to source or source to platform region, UAM performs selective recalculations. Unlike the HBS which performs iterative refinement for calculating coupling from platform to source or source to platform, UAM simulates the source region considering the backscattering from the platform. This allows the UAM to focus on integrating the platform's influence, rather than iterating the same step multiple times. To ensure accuracy, radiation patterns in the azimuth plane are generated with an angular resolution of 1° steps for the FIT, UAM and HBS.

III. HYBRID SOLVER TECHNIQUES FOR A PLPDA MOUNTED ON A UAV

To understand the accuracy and computational efficiency of the UAM when compared with the bidirectional method and full-wave FIT, they were both used for simulating UAVs. As shown in Fig. 1, the PLPDA was mounted 26 cm from the reference base plate of the UAV. The UAV structure consists of several components, such as 3D-printed rectangular blocks made of Polylactic Acid (PLA) with a loss tangent of 0.01 at 2.45 GHz, and a relative dielectric constant of 2.5. The support plates and arms of the UAV are modeled as carbon fiber. Commercially available UAVs are mostly composed of carbon fiber; the conductive nature of carbon fiber can degrade the performance of the PLPDA. To reduce the EM coupling between the UAV

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Fig. 3. Accuracy analysis and simulation time of PLPDA enclosed in a fixture with foam mounted on a UAV.

body and the PLPDA, the PLPDA is mounted far from the UAV body, at a distance of 26 cm. At these distances it is observed that the PLPDA is free from EM coupling [28]. During the simulations, a loss tangent of 0.089 at 2.45 GHz and a relative dielectric constant of 6.5 is considered for carbon fiber [29]. To simulate electrically large structures, such as a UAV with several irregularities in geometry, the IE solver uses MLFMM. MLFMM is a part of MoM that uses surface-based triangular patches and employs a hierarchical tree structure to decompose the computational domain. MLFMM has $O(N \log N)$ complexity while the conventional MoM has $O(N^2)$ complexity for both memory storage and simulation time, where N is the number of unknowns.

The simulated radiation patterns of the PLPDA mounted on the UAV are compared in Fig. 2. Here, the simulation results from the full-wave FIT solver, HBS, and UAM are compared at 0.8, 3.5, 4.3, and 6 GHz. At 0.8 GHz, the PLPDA measured outdoors (with two-UAVs carrying identical PLPDAs and configured separately as transmitter and receiver) are included. From these results, it can be understood that the UAM is a good alternative to the full-wave FIT solver for simulating an antenna mounted on a UAV. In Fig. 3, antenna parameters, such as the realized gain, HPBW, FBR, and simulation time at 0.8, 3.5, 4.3, 6 GHz for the three simulation techniques are compared. From these results, the UAM succeeds in evaluating the performance of a PLPDA mounted on a UAV with a maximum deviation of 0.2 dB in realized gain, 1° in HPBW and, 2 dB in FBR. At a lower frequency such as 0.8 GHz, FIT runs faster than UAM and the HBS method. Therefore, at 0.8 GHz the UAM does not

show any benefit in terms of simulation time. This is due to the relatively stronger EM coupling between the PLPDA and UAV at lower frequencies. At 0.8 GHz, the longest dipole on the PLPDA with a length of 150 mm resonates with the UAV components. Due to the relatively stronger EM coupling, both the HBS and UAM need more simulation time to estimate the performance of the PLPDA in the presence of the UAV body. In particular, the HBS consumes 3.5 hrs to complete the simulation. This is due to three iterations performed by the HBS to meet the convergence criteria.

For higher frequencies, such as 3.5, 4.3, and 6 GHz, the UAM shows a significant reduction in simulation time. At 3.5 GHz it takes 0.7 hrs for the UAM, whereas full-wave FIT requires 2 hrs. At 6 GHz, the UAM is even more efficient, saving several hours of simulation time. With 327 million hexahedral mesh cells, the full-wave FIT completes the simulation in 14 hrs, whereas the UAM completes it in 1.2 hrs. From these comparisons, it is evident that the UAM is effective, particularly at higher frequencies, in reducing the simulation time while maintaining accuracy. UAM, which focuses on the outward propagating fields (source to platform), reduces the complexity in solving Maxwell's equations. On the other hand, the full-wave FIT solver takes several hours to simulate the PLPDA mounted on the UAV to accurately predict the near- and far-field effects of the PLPDA.

In Table II, the convergence behavior of the simulations (PLPDA mounted on the UAV) using the full-wave FIT, HBS, and UAM are presented. For the full-wave FIT, convergence is quantified in terms of the field energy decay and the time

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TABLE II
CONVERGENCE CRITERIA OF FULL-WAVE
FIT AND HYBRID SOLVER TECHNIQUE

Frequency (GHz)	Full-wave FIT (Energy decay, time)	Platform simulated by UAM/HBS (Relative residual, iteration steps)	Source simulated in FIT by UAM/HBS (Energy decay, time)
0.8	-40 dB (64 ns)	1.00×10^{-3} (374)/ 1.00×10^{-3} (383)	-40.4 dB (26 ns)/ -40.6 dB (26 ns)/
3.5	-48.3 dB (24 ns)	9.03×10^{-4} (35)/ 9.76×10^{-4} (34)	-40 dB (14 ns)/ -40 dB (14 ns)
4.3	-103 dB (71 ns)	9.55×10^{-4} (36)/ 9.71×10^{-4} (37)	-40 dB (9 ns)/ -40 dB (9 ns)
6	-60 dB (71 ns)	9.81×10^{-4} (40)/ 9.33×10^{-4} (46)	-40 dB (7 ns)/ -40 dB (7 ns)

required to reach the steady-state monitor threshold. This threshold is defined in the solver settings as an accuracy level of -40 dB, whereas for the IE solver, convergence is defined by an accuracy level of 1.0×10^{-3} . The time (in nanoseconds) reported for the full-wave FIT represents the simulation duration required to achieve a specified -40 dB accuracy. For the IE MoM, the convergence behavior is expressed through the magnitude of the relative residual and the number of iteration steps required to reach the solver's stopping criterion. At 0.8 GHz, the IE solver required 383 iteration steps to achieve a relative residual of 1.0×10^{-3} in the bidirectional setup. At 3.5 GHz, both the UAM and HBS configurations achieved improved convergence with residuals of 9.03×10^{-4} and 9.76×10^{-4} , in 35 and 34 steps, respectively, both better than the defined threshold. The results summarized in Table II indicate that all three simulation approaches met their respective convergence criteria across all frequencies. However, at 0.8 GHz, both the UAM and HBS solvers required significantly more iteration steps (374 and 383, respectively), and the source region required 26 ns to satisfy the convergence condition. In contrast, the simulations at 3.5, 4.3, and 6 GHz converged more quickly, indicating better solver efficiency at higher frequencies. This explains why simulations at 0.8 GHz incurred a longer computational time for the MoM solvers than the full-wave FIT solver.

The computational efficiency of UAM over the HBS can be understood through the computational calculations of each method. In both the techniques, the first step is to solve the source domain. The total time required to solve all the source domains for N_s sources is given by,

$$T_{source} = \Sigma N_s T_s, \quad (3)$$

where N_s is the number of source domains and T_s is the time required to solve each source domain in the transient solver (FIT). Considering that we have only one platform, the total time required to simulate the platform is given by,

$$T_{platform} = T_p, \quad (4)$$

where T_p denotes the time required to simulate the platform. After the source and platform are simulated individually in the

Transient and IE based on the FIT and MoM techniques respectively, the next important step is evaluating the EM coupling between them. This involves computing the EM coupling from source to platform and platform to the source domain. For N_s source domain, EM coupling from the platform is considered for each source domain. The total time required in evaluating this recoupling is given by,

$$T_{recoupling} = \Sigma N_s T_s, \quad (5)$$

and the total simulation time in simulating the PLPDA mounted on the UAV using UAM is given by,

$$T_{total\ UAM} = \Sigma N_s T_s + T_p + \Sigma N_s T_s, \quad (6)$$

In the case of HBS, the total simulation time is given by,

$$T_{total\ HBS} = N_{iter} (N_s T_s + T_p), \quad (7)$$

where N_{iter} is the number of iterations performed by the HBS to calculate the EM coupling from the source to the platform and platform to the source. These iterations are based on the generalized Minimal Residual method and the number of iterations performed designates the Krylov iterations. For the HBS to converge, the stopping criteria for the iterations are defined by providing the maximum number of iterations or target residual before starting the simulation. The iterative solver stops when either the maximal number of iterations or the specified target residual of 0.01 in our case, is reached. UAM focuses on dominant wave propagation, where the fields predominantly travel from the PLPDA source to the UAV platform region. By focusing on dominant wave propagation, the UAM does not have to solve the full set of Maxwell's equations in all directions, unlike full-wave FIT solvers [30]. This simplification in solving Maxwell's equations helps to reduce the size of the computational domain. Although UAM focuses on dominant wave propagation, i.e. wave propagation from source to platform, it succeeds in achieving accuracy by considering the backscattering from the platform. At higher frequencies, such as 6 GHz, the majority of EM fields from an antenna tend to propagate in the dominant direction, i.e. away from the PLPDA towards the UAV. Under these conditions, the backscattering from the UAV body becomes relatively weak. This weak backscattering at higher frequencies helps the UAM to simulate the PLPDA mounted on the UAV in less time. In this way, UAM strikes a balance between accuracy and computational load, making it computationally efficient. The computational efficiency of UAM in terms of RAM usage and GPU usage over the HBS and full-wave FIT is described in Fig. 4. As shown in Fig. 4, UAM uses relatively less computational resources at 0.8, 3.5, 4.3, and 6 GHz. At 0.8 GHz, UAM utilizes 5 times less RAM than the full-wave FIT, and at 6 GHz it uses 2.2 times less RAM than its counterpart. Though HBS is also computationally more efficient than full-wave FIT, UAM succeeds in completing the simulations with less resources than the HBS. At 0.8 GHz, UAM uses 3 times less memory than the

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bidirectional method and 1.7 times less memory at 6 GHz. In

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Computational efficiency of UAM for PLPDA mounted on a UAV.

terms of GPU usage, both UAM and HBS use the same amount of GPU, which is less than the GPU utilization of full-wave FIT.

TABLE III
GPU ACCELERATION FOR THE PLATFORM

Simulation Method at 0.8 GHz	Simulation Time (hrs)	GPU Usage (GB)	RAM Usage (GB)
UAM/HBS with only source accelerated by Nvidia RTX4090	1.2/3.5	2.4/2.4	4.8/14.2
UAM/HBS with both source and platform accelerated by Nvidia RTX4090	1/2.2	14.2/14.3	4.8/18.4
UAM/HBS with both source and platform accelerated by Nvidia GP100	0.5/1.5	16.9/17.6	4.8/20.8
Full-wave FIT accelerated by Nvidia RTX4090	1.1	7.2	24

At 0.8 GHz, the HBS takes 3.5 hrs to complete the simulation. To reduce the simulation time, GPU acceleration is enabled for the platform as well along with the source. A single-precision GPU, such as the Nvidia RTX4090, and a double-precision GPU, such as the Nvidia GP100, were used at separate instances in these simulations. The simulation method for the UAM and bidirectional involves GPU acceleration for the source simulated in the FIT and the platform simulated in the MoM. In Table III, the simulation time, GPU usage, and RAM usage for UAM and HBS at 0.8 GHz are presented. In this table, we compare the UAM/HBS with the source accelerated by the Nvidia RTX 4090 with no GPU acceleration for the platform, UAM/HBS with both the source and the platform accelerated by the Nvidia RTX4090, UAM/HBS with both the source and the platform accelerated by the Nvidia GP100 GPU, and the full-wave FIT accelerated by the Nvidia RTX4090 GPU. From these comparisons it can be observed that the UAM/HBS with both source and platform accelerated by the Nvidia GP100 GPU shows benefit in terms of simulation time when compared to UAM/HBS with both source and platform accelerated by the Nvidia RTX4090 GPU, and UAM/HBS with only the source accelerated by the Nvidia

RTX4090 GPU. This improvement is due to the use of double-precision computations on the Nvidia GP100 GPU. Double precision GPUs uses 64 bits to represent floating-point values, which reduces round-off errors in iterative solvers and allows the simulation to converge in fewer iterations, effectively reducing the total simulation time. However, this comes at the expense of relatively higher GPU usage. In contrast, single precision uses 32 bits per value, which requires less GPU memory but can accumulate numerical errors hence results in higher number of iterations to meet the convergence criteria, resulting in longer overall simulation times despite lower memory usage. In terms of radiation patterns, irrespective of the GPU used, UAM/HBS with both source and platform accelerated by the GPUs shows the same performance as the UAM/HBS method with the source accelerated by the GPU in the FIT and no GPU acceleration for the platform in the MoM. From these comparisons it can be concluded that when running hybrid solver simulations to simulate an antenna mounted on an electrically large platform it is advised to use GPU acceleration only for the source domain.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed the use of the unidirectional advanced hybrid solver method for simulating a PLPDA mounted on an electrically large structure, such as a UAV. This method has been validated by comparing the radiation patterns of the PLPDA from UAM with those obtained from the HBS and full-wave FIT solvers. From these comparisons in terms of antenna parameters, such as realized gain, HRPBW, FBR, and computational efficiency, it is observed that UAM maintains relatively good accuracy, similar to a full-wave FIT solver. In terms of computational efficiency, UAM is an efficient hybrid solver technique when compared to HBS. For PLPDA enclosed in a fixture with foam mounted on a UAV, the UAM is 1.3 times faster than the HBS and 12 times faster than the full-wave FIT solver at 6 GHz. Furthermore, in terms of GPU usage, UAM requires 2.5 times less GPU than the full-wave FIT at 6 GHz.

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